

GMOS-FR (Global Mercury Observation System – FRance) Research Data Management Plan for Atmospheric Mercury datasets (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM data)

Research Data Management Plan created using DMP OPIDoR, (French ANR - DMP template (english) template)

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About the GMOS-FR DMP

The GMOS-FR Research Data Management Plan (DMP) is related to Atmospheric Mercury Data Repository in France and describes how atmospheric mercury data issued from derived 2011-2015 GMOS FP7 spin-off programs and projects (GMOS_{Stral}-1028 IPEV program, Pic du Midi, Chacaltaya and La Reunion atmospheric mercury short time projects) are handled. The goal is to i) document the key elements of the GMOS related atmospheric mercury (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM compounds) data management life cycle, ii) describe how the data are collected, processed and generated in the course of the dedicated related programs and projects, iii) detail the technical solutions to manage, archive, curate and access the data, and iv) outline the strategy and development needed for making related atmospheric mercury (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM) data FAIR.

Atmospheric mercury data in GMOS-FR are derived from measurements made in programs and projects embedded in GOS4M (Global Observation System for Mercury) network, a GEO (Group on Earth Observations) flagship aimed to support the Minamata Convention on mercury secretariat, the UN Environment mercury fate and transport partnership and all Nations in the follow up of the Conferences of Parties (COP) related to the Effectiveness Evaluation and Global Monitoring framework. GOS4M is federating existing regional and monitoring network and work closely with Nations in providing assistance and promote capacity building for filling existing geographical gaps in the global monitoring. GOS4M is consequently built on existing networks and observing infrastructures and provides a link to the Global Mercury Observation System (GMOS – www.gmos.eu) from which GMOS_{Stral}-1028 IPEV program, the major research program providing data in GMOS-FR, was initially created.

GMOS-FR DMP is linked to the GMOS-FR AERIS web data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>), led by PI Olivier Magand and Aurelien Dommergue, and supported by Damien Boulanger via AERIS, a french atmospheric Data and Service center (<https://en.aeris-data.fr/>). As both PIs practice open science and scholarship, the present DMP puts an emphasis on data sharing and reuse. All data and milestone working documents will be made available freely in online repositories throughout the research project and all publications will be published open access. The DMP is structured and based on a template created for the DMP OPIDoR and is a living document that is expected to be revised regularly as the project evolves. The goal is to make the DMP accessible for all stakeholders (repository operators, funders, researchers, publishers, infrastructure providers etc.).

Associated website

- GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>)
- GMOS_{Stral}-1028 IPEV program presentation (<https://www.ige-grenoble.fr/GMOSStral-Observations-et-chimie-du> and https://institut-polaire.fr/fr/programmes_soutenus/observations-planetaires-du-mercure-atmospherique-contributions-et-etudes-des-processus-en-regions-sub-antarctique-et-en-antarctique/)
- GMOS website (<http://www.gmos.eu/>)
- GOS4M website (<http://www.gos4m.org/>)
- Minamata Convention on Mercury (<https://www.mercuryconvention.org/en>)

Associated funding

Funding started in November, 2017 for GMOS-FR AERIS data portal and in November 2011 for GMOSStral-1028 IPEV program.

- European Commission : FP7-ENVIRONMENT (Grant agreement ID : 265113)
- French Polar institute (IPEV – Institut Polaire Paul-Emile Victor)
- CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique) with dedicated ANR and/or INSU-LEFE-CHAT (Atmospheric Chemistry) research national project
- OSUG@2020 Labex Grenoble Alpes University Research project
- AERIS (French Data and Services Cluster for Atmosphere)

Associated partners

- French Polar Institute (IPEV – Institut Polaire Paul-Emile Victor) - FRANCE
- French Southern and Antarctic Lands (TAAF – Terres Australes et Antarctiques Françaises) – FRANCE
- Centre National de Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) - FRANCE
- Grenoble Alpes University (UGA) – FRANCE
- Toulouse Environment and Geosciences laboratory (GET) Observatoire Midi Pyrénées - FRANCE
- CNR Institute of Atmospheric Pollution Research, Division of Rende – ITALY
- Atmosphere and Cyclone laboratory (LACY) La Reunion University – France
- Observatory of Atmospheric Physics of Reunion (OPAR-OSU-Reunion) – France
- Atmospheric physics laboratory (LFA-UMSA) - BOLIVIA

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GMOS-FR DMP versions

GMOS-FR Data Management Plan version 3.1 - November 28, 2022 version

Date	Version #	Status	Author	Author's affiliation	Approved by	Validation date
05/12/2022	3.1	Rearrangement of the sections, new additional workflow	Olivier MAGAND	IGE, Grenoble (UMR5001)	Damien BOULANGER	05/12/2022
23/05/2022	3.0	DOI related GMOS-FR data, modification of the workflow scheme, use of ANR_DMP_template_english_v4	Olivier MAGAND	IGE, Grenoble (UMR5001)	Damien BOULANGER	16/11/2022
01/07/2021	2.0	Rearrangement of the sections, addition of the data conservation part and backup redundancy with GRICAD	Olivier MAGAND	IGE, Grenoble (UMR5001)		
16/03/2020	1.0	DMP edition	Olivier MAGAND	IGE, Grenoble (UMR5001)		

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1. GMOS-FR abstract

Atmospheric mercury data for GMOS-FR are derived from 2011-2015 GMOS FP7 program and spin-off projects (GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program – atmospheric monitoring study - and short time-limited atmospheric research projects such as in France – Pic du Midi station -, Bolivia – Chacaltaya station -, or La Reunion island – Maido Observatory -). Most of the GMOS-FR data are issued from GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program.

The overall goal of GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program is to follow the development of a more than one decade-created coordinated global observation system for mercury (2011-2015 GMOS FP7-environment Grant agreement ID: 265113, www.gmos.eu) which is able to provide temporal and spatial distributions of mercury (Hg) concentrations in ambient air and precipitation over land and over surface waters at different altitudes and latitudes around the world (continuous monitoring measurements). This provides high quality data for the validation and application of regional and global scale atmospheric models, to give to governments, national and international organizations and stakeholders a firm basis for future policy development and implementation. Goals of the GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program are (a) to continue the development of atmospheric mercury species monitoring (ambient concentrations and deposition fluxes of mercury species) in polar (Antarctic) and subpolar/subtropical (sub Antarctic territories) areas by continuous monitoring from permanent ground-based stations; (b) to validate regional and global scale atmospheric mercury modelling systems able to predict temporal variations and spatial distributions of atmospheric mercury entering to and re-emitted from terrestrial and aquatic receptors; (c) to evaluate and identify source-receptor relationships and their temporal trends for current and projected scenarios of mercury emissions from anthropogenic and natural sources; (d) to develop interoperable tools to allow the sharing of observational and models output data produced. In this context, GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program have set up three continuous mercury measurement stations in the sub Antarctic/sub-tropical (Amsterdam island) and Antarctic (Dumont d'Urville, Concordia) regions to document and monitor atmospheric variations of mercury in remote regions of the Southern Hemisphere, and to work on the poorly known reactivity, cycling, deposition and re-emission of this compound in these areas. Initially funding by European Commission and French Polar Institute (see funding section), GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program is now mostly funded by French Polar Institute and CNRS national research projects.

The overall goal of short time-limited mercury atmospheric research projects (France – Pic du Midi station -, Bolivia – Chacaltaya station -, or La Reunion island – Maido Observatory -) is not as ambitious as that of GMOSTral-1028 IPEV program, but there are a number of science target similarities. Documentation and monitoring of atmospheric mercury species in remote and/or geographically specific regions have been a key objective of these short-term projects, complementary to what is being done in GMOSTral-1028 monitoring IPEV one.

Several atmospheric mercury species and products have been measured, collected, qualified, and archived since the program's start in 2011. The present GMOS-FR DMP addresses the data management life cycle of Total or Gaseous Elemental Mercury (TGM/GEM), Gaseous Oxidized Mercury (GOM) and Particulate Bound Mercury (PBM) and Reactive Mercury (RM being the sum of GOM and PBM) in Dumont-D'Urville and Concordia stations (DDU and DCC/DMC, respectively, in Antarctica), Amsterdam subtropical island (AMS, sub Antarctic-subtropical district), Pic du midi mountain site (PDM – French Pyrenees monitoring station), Chacaltaya high elevation monitoring station (CHC, Bolivia) and La Reunion island site (MAIDO French observatory) from 2011 to nowadays. All previously listed mercury compounds are not systematically collected in every cited observation station and not over the whole period from 2011 to the present. Each measuring station listed in GMOS-FR has its own measurement time frame and is associated with some or all of the listed compounds.

2. DATA DESCRIPTION AND COLLECTION OR RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

2a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

GMOSStral-1028 IPEV program and short time-limited projects atmospheric mercury data (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM) are collected through dedicated measurements techniques and methodologies precisely described in the following papers : Angot et al., 2014 (www.atmos-chem-phys.net/14/11461/2014/doi:10.5194/acp-14-11461-2014) ; Angot et al., 2016a (www.atmos-chem-phys.net/16/8265/2016/doi:10.5194/acp-16-8265-2016) ; Maruszczak et al., 2017 (<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b04999>) ; Slemr et al., 2020 (<https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-7683-2020>) and Cairns et al., 2021 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2021.118634>). Dedicated software, data treatment (comprising QA-QC issues) as well as storage and backup processes are described in sections 3 and 4 (see also Figure 1).

Atmospheric mercury data concerned by the GMOS-FR DMP were and are collected from 2011 in six atmospheric monitoring stations (Dumont-D'Urville – DDU – and Dome Concordia – DCC or DMC -, from Antarctic sites ; Amsterdam island – AMS – in subtropical/sub Antarctic station ; Pic du Midi – PDM – in French Pyrenees ; Chacaltaya – CHC – from high elevation tropical site in Bolivia and Mado observatory – MAIDO – in tropical Reunion island in Indian ocean) with three of them (AMS, DDU, DCC/DMC) being incorporated in the GMOSStral-1028 IPEV program ("Global Mercury Observations: atmospheric monitoring and process studies in sub Antarctic regions and Antarctic lands¹). Five of six stations were or are still coordinated by IGE (Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement) and one was managed by GET (Toulouse Environment and Geosciences laboratory) (see partners section).

All above mentioned programs produced 4 main levels of data and data products: these are represented by raw data and the numbers 0, 1 and 2 (*step 0 – Data acquisition and extraction* – Figure 1 related to GMOS-FR data processing workflow). Only levels 1 and 2 data are freely available and downloadable (open access on <https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>; AERIS website data portal managed both by AERIS DSC - Data Service Center - SEDOO and IGE and called GMOS-FR ; see sections 3 and 4) for (inter)national research communities as well as public and non-commercial purpose uses (CC BY-NC 4.0 licence).

Raw data are information directly obtained from human measurements or automated sensors that have not undergone any transformation. They provide quantitative and qualitative information about physical variables of the environment (.txt files). Raw data are not shared outside directly concerned program members.

Level 0 data are data in physical units either directly provided by instruments or converted from engineering units (for example, mV, mA, Ω) to physical units from raw data. Level 0 data are filtered by quality-checking process. They are data that are generated as intermediate steps in the data processing of levels 1 (fully qualified) or 2 (elaborated data product) data preparation, and for this reason they are not initially handled as persistent data and not shared outside directly concerned program members. L0 data are presented in .xlsx and/or .txt format.

Level 1 data are the quality-checked dataset following international SOP, with data in original time resolution acquisition, ready to be distributed through the freely accessible GMOS-FR AERIS data portal. Data L1 users have to keep in mind that, even if L1 data provides high-quality checked dataset, this one may be improved for more elaborated data product, depending of the study scope. L1 data are presented in .csv and/or .txt interoperable format.

Level 2 data are data products that are based on L1 GMOS-FR observational data. L2 data can be presented at the GMOS-FR AERIS data portal as an elaborated product. L2 data are presented in .csv and/or .txt interoperable format.

As strictly noted in GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal, data (levels 1 and 2 only; raw data and Level 0 being not available and downloadable) are freely available for non-commercial use for public and research community (CC BY-NC 4.0 licence). They can then be (re)use if and only if with respect of the data policy described in "Data policy and contact" section in GMOS-FR AERIS data portal (see section 6).

2b. What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

As previously pointed out, data format is in .csv, .txt and/or .xlsx, and annual volume storage – by observation site – is closed to only few tens of megabytes; the .csv and .txt ones only being interoperable. In case of missing information, a request for supplementary documents can be made to the program managers and/or GMOS-FR data PIs.

¹ GMOSStral IPEV program presentation (https://www.ige-grenoble.fr/GMOSStral-Observations-et-chimie-du-polaire.fr/fr/programmes_soutenus/observations-planetaires-du-mercure-atmospherique-contributions-et-etudes-des-processus-en-regions-sub-antarctique-et-en-antarctique/)

3. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY

3a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

In order to increase their reuse, the accessible GMOS-FR data (levels 1 and 2) are completed by metadata (free access on the GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal) whose data source (*step 2 – Data transformation* – Figure 1). The data accessible via GMOS-FR are organized by AERIS (see sections 3 and 4) according to the wishes of the GMOS-FR team. The GMOS-FR site and the referenced articles named below (and associated ones) in section 2, clearly describe the processing procedures for the transition from raw data to L2 levels, the methods for dealing with the problems and the set of metrological processes applied with respect to the required international standards (*step 1 – Data examination and cleaning* – Figure 1). Each downloadable qualified data set (L1 and L2) is also assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) by AERIS, depending on the qualification level and the site considered.

Figure 1: Illustration of GMOS-FR data processing workflow.

3b. What data quality control measures will be used?

To ensure the comparability and the quality of the mercury measurements regardless of the study site, each dedicated instrument on-site and all data are respectively operated and treated according to international Standard Operation Procedures (SOP) as described in well-established regional and international mercury monitoring networks (GMOS, CAMNet, AMNet).

Quality control procedures are consequently well defined and are applied at each step of the data processing chain, from the raw measurement to the provision of the qualified data. Standardized QA measures and calibration tools are applied at measurement platforms on-site to provide documented and traceable data and data products. Raw dataset, routine, exceptional maintenance as well as monitoring files are compiled and processed by dedicated-software (« DataSplitter » software created under Visual Basic programming language) developed at the IGE (Institute of Environmental Geosciences, UMR5001) and specifically designed to quality assure and quality control atmospheric mercury datasets in order to produce final clean data time series. In this automated process, the raw dataset is compared against potential flags corresponding to more than 40 criteria that specifically refer to all operation phases related to the calculation of mercury concentrations, calibration and parameters checking related to the integrity of the correct running of the instruments. Each raw observation is individually flagged depending on the result of each corresponding criterion and returns, as a temporary output, a flagged dataset (valid, warning, and invalid). Inclusion of all field notes, implying corrections and data invalidation regrouped in the flagged dataset step, as well as a clarification step by the site manager according to their knowledge allows for the production of a complete quality-assured and

quality-controlled dataset according to the initial temporal acquisition resolution (*step 1 – Data examination and cleaning* – Figure 1). A detailed description of these procedures is available in the GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (GMOS-FR data products section).

Finally, GMOS-FR atmospheric mercury (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM) data has four main levels of data and data products : these are represented by raw data and the numbers 0, 1 and 2. Only levels 1 and 2 QA/QC qualified data are available and downloadable on GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>).

4. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE RESEARCH PROCESS

4a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

On field, raw data are read and processed by the dedicated acquisition software (TekCap from ©Tekran) installed on each field computer related to the acquisition instrument. The raw data configured in .txt format are daily backed-up stored on each field in the observing stations themselves (acquisition PC-related instrument + redundancy on a local storage device as NAS type - Network Attached Storage -) as well as in IGE (for AMS, DDU, DMC/DCC, CHC and MAIDO data) and GET (for PDM data), also on computer, thanks to an automatic daily sending (email) generated by each IT services on site (*step 0 - Data acquisition and extraction* – Figure 1). Related metadata file generated on site are also double-stored on the same dedicated storage space.

In IGE (as well as in GET), raw data and associated information (routine, exceptional maintenance and monitoring files) are compiled and processed by home-made dedicated-software (« DataSplitter ») in order to produce final clean data (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM) time series (*step 1 – Data examination and cleaning* – Figure 1). One of DataSplitter software production is notably the L0 data which are the data-treatment processing link between raw and final qualified data. L0 data are on .xlsx format. All produced qualified data (comprising the ones managed by GET) (L1 and L2 in .csv or .txt files format), as raw and L0 dataset, are stored in redundancy in IGE on data treatment dedicated-computer as well as in SUMMER backup UGA data center located in GRICAD Grenoble Alpes Research - Scientific Computing and Data Infrastructure (*step 3 – Data load, sharing and preservation* – Figure 1). Back-up in SUMMER data center is automatically operated twice by week. GRICAD is based on NetApp manufacturer's technologies. It can accommodate volumes up to several petabytes and offers advanced functions ensuring security, data integrity and service continuity.

Ideally once every six months and at least once a year, the final-guarantee qualified data are uploaded (dedicated FTP server with password restricted access) in GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>) (*step 3 – Data load, sharing and preservation* – Figure 1).

GMOS-FR uploaded data are secured and archived by the SEDOO one of the AERIS Data and Services Centre (DSC) with extensive computing and data storage resources (Figures 1 and 2). In the case that the data would be lost, a sustainable archiving is provided by a dedicated service at SEDOO. The data is duplicated on different geographical sites in France.

Figure 2: Illustration of AERIS operating diagram.

4b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care during the research

At the stage of updated DMP version, no sensitive data will be collected in the framework of GMOS-FR. The data are from scientific measurements of mercury atmospheric composition and other related quantities.

In the event of data loss, the intent is to make use of the redundant copies of the data at the various cited locations and/or the sustainable archiving data provided by dedicated service at SEDOO thanks to duplication process on different geographical sites in France.

5. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS, CODE OF CONDUCT

5a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

The GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>), where atmospheric mercury (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM) L1 and L2 data are available and downloadable, does not store the personal data of potential data (re)users, as no registration is required to download qualified data. The data are derived from scientific measurements of atmospheric composition and other related quantities.

5b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

All data collected are the property of the GMOS-FR science and technical team (projects managers, instrument PIs, measurement and data treatment dedicated people) and/or institutions and/or international networks in which they are integrated and to which they must respond. GMOS-FR team agrees to share data, once qualified, stored and downloadable in the GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>) with the wider scientific community and the public. Since these data are collected during a project supported by national and/or international public funds, the data are ultimately owned by the public in agreement with CNRS Open Science National Plan. To

remind, only L1 and L2 GMOS-FR atmospheric mercury data are freely available and downloadable and exclusively for non-commercial use.

5c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be considered?

The GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>), where atmospheric mercury (TGM/GEM/GOM/PBM/RM) L1 and L2 qualified data are available and downloadable, does not manage any data with disclosure risk.

The data providers (GMOS-Stral-1028 program and time-limited projects managers, GMOS-FR data PI) are well aware of their responsibility for the correctness of data and metadata. In general, everyone should work in a socially ethical way keeping the integrity and FAIRness, and maintaining a high level of trust and respect among the people working in the different program / projects and with the users and other stakeholders. One should always consider that the mission of all above-mentioned research studies is to provide effective access for a wide user community to its resources and services, in order to facilitate high-quality atmospheric chemistry research, to increase the excellence in Earth system research, and to provide information and knowledge on developing sustainable solutions to societal challenges.

6. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

6a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

The GMOS-FR AERIS data portal include information about the data produced in the framework of GMOS-Stral-1028 IPEV program and short time-limited projects, and the ones being freely sharable, available and downloadable (<https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>). All data are distributed under a CC-BY 4.0 licence (*step 3 – Data load, sharing and preservation* – Figure 1). This licence allows potential reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to data creators (GMOS-FR website data portal PIs) and that reusers respect the defined data policy described in the dedicated section in <https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>.

Atmospheric mercury species data stored in GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal are public data open to all data users (no registration to get access). As previously noted, users are free to copy the material in any medium or format, remix, transform, and build upon the material for any research science purpose, except for commercial use (*steps 4 and 5 – Data analysis and interpretation + Publication and diffusion* – Figure 1). Users envisaging to publish a paper should consider at an early stage:

- to inform the GMOS-FR web portal PIs (Dr O. Magand – olivier.magand@cnr.fr, Pr A. Dommergue – aurelien.dommergue@univ-grenoble-alpes.fr) as well as other contacts possibly related to the data used (see in contact section in the selected dataset in <https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>) in the framework of a research paper preparation ;
- to grant data providers the opportunity to review the use of the data and conclusions drawn from it, and optionally, to offer co-authorship to the GMOS-FR website portal PIs and related contacts if the GMOS-FR data are essential to the work;
- to cite relevant papers from the GMOS-FR website portal PIs, related contact and GMOS-FR;
- to cite the unique and persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier – DOI – in the present discussed database) corresponding to site and data levels used;
- to not redistribute the data;
- to include acknowledgements in publications recognizing the GMOS-FR data provision with different statements following sites (see “Data policy and contact” section in <https://gmos.aeris-data.fr/>). Following sentence has also to be cited in acknowledgements section **the [products/database] GMOS-FR is maintained by the French national center for Atmospheric data and services AERIS**; [products/database] being the considered level (L1 and/or L2) and station (AMS, CHC, DDU, DMC or DCC, PDM, MAIDO).

The GMOS-FR L1 and L2 qualified final data are the most important data for long-term archival even if all program and projects managers expect also to manage the best as possible raw data and L0 archives in the same temporal term. To remind, raw and L0 data are not initially handled as persistent data (see section 1a). Consequently, only L1 and L2 qualified data and related elaborated data products are made openly available to the public. They will be distributed over AERIS DSC via GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal whereas raw and L0 data would be only stored and not distributed also via GMOS-FR. Raw and L0 data are only available for the program and projects managers and few project members as their quality is limited.

6b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

AERIS has experts in computer hardware and software. Their expertise is employed to ensure data is backed up regularly and safely (see section 4a). The mid-term preservation (10 years) is guaranteed by AERIS (see section 7a). The question of long-term preservation will be addressed soon in the framework of Data Terra RI. In case any of the DSC (Data Service Center) finds it cannot maintain this database, the responsibility could be transferred to another data center within AERIS. AERIS is strongly supported at national level (CNRS, CNES, Meteo-France...). In the highly unlikely event that AERIS will not have capacity to maintain GMOS-FR website data portal, and consequently, will close “archives and distributions” operations, GMOS-FR related program and project managers guarantee that they will migrate all content to other suitable repositories, and since all datasets will have DOIs (see section 3a and 6d), all citations and links to datasets will not be affected. To remind, raw/L0/L1-L2 GMOS-FR data and metadata files (routine, exceptional maintenance and monitoring files) are stored also in redundancy in IGE on data treatment dedicated-computer as well as in SUMMER backup UGA data center located in GRICAD Grenoble Alpes Research - Scientific Computing and Data Infrastructure; back-up in SUMMER data center being automatically operated twice by week (see section 4a).

6c. What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

Qualified L1 and L2 data are easily and freely accessible and downloadable from GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal. Access to the data doesn't require intervention or handling of requests. The website being permanently accessed, qualified data can be immediately downloaded. No specific method or software tool are needed for L1 and L2 access. These last qualified data are downloadable in an interoperable format (.csv and/or .txt) that is easy to use and manipulate. Raw data and L0 data are, on the contrary, only accessible by restricted FTP access for GMOS-FR data PI and GMOS-FR AERIS database manager.

6d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

One of the services of AERIS is to provide a DOI for each dataset (*step 3 – Data load, sharing and preservation – Figure 1*). AERIS has an agreement to assign DOIs to datasets with the prefix 10.25326. A DOI is consequently assigned for fully L1 and L2 qualified data in GMOS-FR AERIS data portal. It is registered on Datacite (<https://datacite.org/>) using its metadata scheme. The landing GMOS-FR page contains a sample citation, full metadata and information on how to access the data.

For the internal datasets (raw data and non-fully qualified data), non-persistent homemade identifiers are generated. A new system based on ePIC handles is currently under implementation. AERIS already has an agreement to assign such PIDs with the prefix 21.11148. An ePIC PID may also be assigned to all raw and L0 data in the future.

7. DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

7a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

The GMOS-FR DMP will be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure its content reflects the intent and needs of the related program and projects and international related networks science team (GMOS, GOS4M) and the public interested in GMOS-FR and GEO-GOS4M scientific and activities issues.

GMOSStral-1028 IPEV program and short time projects managers and notably the associated data steward (= data manager program) are responsible for all activities related to data management from data capture to archiving and sharing.

GMOS-FR AERIS website data portal managers and related people are responsible for GMOS-FR website portal maintenance and upkeep, in strong collaboration with GMOS-FR science and technical team being also strongly involved in GMOSStral-1028 IPEV program. The mid-term preservation (10 years) is guaranteed by AERIS SEDOO Data Service Center.

7b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

AERIS ensure that the GMOS-FR data is FAIR.

Data management is under the responsibility of GMOS-FR scientific and technical program manager, who meets the objectives and FAIR principles recommended for the management and sharing of mercury monitoring data within GEO-GOS4M, in connection with the work of the Minamata international convention. The technical manager of GMOS-Stral-1028 program, clearly identified to the partners, is in charge of coordinating data management for the whole project (= GMOS-FR data steward). Each partner has to define a "data correspondent" responsible for the management of the data produced in his team for the identified sites. The data correspondent has to transmit all the necessary information to the GMOS-FR data steward to establish and update the data management plan. The GMOS-FR data steward updates and submits the GMOS-FR Research DMP when necessary and sends it to the data correspondents each time a new version is released. The GMOS-FR data steward is responsible for

- Verifying the data quality: structure, format and naming according to the recommendations of the data management plan;

- Verifying that metadata are correctly filled in;

- transferring the data to the GMOS-FR AERIS database.

The GMOS-FR data steward and correspondents may change during the project and any changes will be recorded in the data management plan.

Financial effort is provided through the recruitment of a PhD student and a postdoc, who will be in charge of the management of the data they will produce respectively. This will be completed by time used by the PI to coordinate the whole data management.